

Shared Software Environments for Heliophysics

Report from the IHDEA Science Platforms Working Group

Brian Thomas¹, Shawn Polson², Jan Reerink³, Rebecca Ringuette^{1,4}, Alex Antunes⁵, James Colliander⁶, Arnaud Masson³, Julie Barnum², Laura Hayes⁷, James Parr⁸, Anne Spalding⁸, Jeffery Bradford^{1,4}, Sarah Rourke^{1,4}, Jon Vandegriff⁵, and Omar Shalaby^{1,4}

1. Goddard Space Flight Center/NASA, Greenbelt, MD 20771

2. Laboratory for Atmospheric and Space Physics, Boulder, CO 80303

3. European Space Agency (ESA), European Space Astronomy Centre (ESAC), Camino Bajo del Castillo s/n, 286te92 Villanueva de la Cañada, Madrid, Spain

4. ADNET Systems, Inc.

5. Johns Hopkins Applied Physics Laboratory, Laurel, MD 20707

6. 2i2c, 3439 SE Hawthorne Blvd #247, Portland, OR 97214-5048

7. Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies, DIAS Dunsink Observatory, Dublin, D15 XR2R, Ireland.

8. Trillium Technologies Inc, 8668 John Hickman Pkwy, STE 301, Frisco, TX 75034

Abstract

Making software work across platforms is currently a challenging engineering task but modern approaches to software engineering and development are making it attainable. In the past decades shared software environments have come into a mature state. It is possible to create and use these shared software environments on different platforms. This greatly facilitates sharing and using software between computers. The premise of these shared software environments is that they 'just work', regardless of the platform, and decrease user time spent resolving dependencies and related software installation challenges. Furthermore, we believe that open science, which has the goal of creating transparent and reproducible results, will require such solutions since much of our research today relies on creating and/or repurposing existing software to do science.

In this paper we describe the efforts of the IHDEA Science Platforms group to engineer a small set of basic shared environments for doing heliophysics research using Python software. These software environments include a range of implementations ranging from virtual environments to containerized environments as well as container-backed platforms, like JupyterLab, which may be hosted remotely in the cloud or institutional compute environments. We present use cases, our work to identify key software in use by the community, our analysis to understand the types of shared software environments that would be of the most use to the community

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The Problem

Today it is common for science research to now depend on software, such as models, analysis or pipeline processing code, to produce new science results. New open science initiatives require that researchers make their research more transparent and reproducible (see Gong 2022 and references therein). Given our dependency on software, this effectively levies a requirement that the specific software used be referenceable and ideally 'shareable'. A typical issue with sharing is the "it doesn't work for me" problem; it is too hard to match the software environment needed in order to install or run the desired software on a different platform. This may be because of a mismatch in the OS between where the software was developed and the implementing platform, lack of specialized tooling to build or run the software, outdated dependencies, or challenging dependency collisions with software in the target environment. Without expert knowledge of the software, and/or some advanced skills with computer programming, it is often too much work for the average research scientist to run research software created by other researchers. This is a critical barrier to research transparency - a pillar of open science - that can now be resolved with the technology of our day.

The Technical Solution

Investigators interested in research software created by others need to have an easier means to readily run it. One means to facilitate this is to create a set of basic shared software environments which may be easily imported and built upon.

Various technologies are already available to provide the solution we need and have been noted by others previously (for example Howe 2012 and Hurley, Budden & Crampin 2015). Virtual software environments may be created using conda (Anaconda Software Distribution, 2020), virtualenv (Virtualenv Software Distribution, 2024), and containerized compute approaches such as Docker (Merkel 2014) and are already in widespread use by the computer engineering community. Various layers of implementation, ranging from virtual environments to shared compute platforms such as ESA Datalabs (<https://datalabs.esa.int>) or cloud-based ones like 2i2c (<https://2i2c.org/>) or HelioCloud (<https://heliocloud.org>; Thomas et al. 2022) can help to make researcher software more accessible to the community (see Figure 1). Our work incorporates these technologies and implementations for finding a solution.

Figure 1. Shows 3 levels of implementation of shared software environments (by row). Starting from the top, virtual software environments such as anaconda or virtualenv allow anyone to pull in the software environment to their machine. The next row involves taking that engineered environment and making it the default environment within a container image (such as Docker, Merkel 2014). This image may then be marshalled into sharable containers. Finally, the bottom row indicates that the container may back a notebooking environment (such as Jupyter, Kluyver et al. 2016) which can be hosted in a shared compute platform (such as the cloud). The top layer requires the least amount of specialized infrastructure effort while the bottom layer requires significant engineering of the shared platform. In all cases the shared environment may be extended to support custom researcher software.

We have investigated creating container images based on whether non-GPU or GPU/Machine Learning tooling is needed (similar to the Pangeo project, see <https://pangeo.io>). The PyHC and HelioCloud project images represent some of the initial attempts (Polson 2024 and Thomas 2024 respectively) and we have found that lumping all of the possible heliophysics software packages desired into the virtual environment results in fairly large images; for example, the non-GPU HelioCloud image is approximately ~7 GB uncompressed. This large size is directly related to the large number of software packages and their 3rd party dependencies which are included. The problem with this large image size is that it is prohibitive to use in remote hosted platforms (it significantly slows marshalling for the user sessions) and the large number of software packages also makes dependency resolution slow, and at times challenging, which poses a problem for consumers who may wish to tailor their images by adding packages to the default provided environment. Instead, we decided to create multiple shared software environments with smaller, more focused solutions geared towards supporting the actual tasks performed by the community.

Survey to Understand Needed Environment(s)

The missing critical part of the solution is identifying which heliophysics-oriented software we should include in these virtual environments. We have conducted a study of the community to understand the use cases for research software which should be supported. As the python language (van Rossum 1995) is increasingly popular with heliophysics researchers, we made that the focus of our effort. We polled the community asking them to describe the python research software they were creating and using and why (see QR code and link below for the specific survey questions). The community polling was performed at the CEDAR and SHINE meetings in 2024, by emailing the PyHC email list, and through inclusion in a HDRL virtual user workshop in late 2024. These communities taken together may be used to get an approximate size of the Heliophysics community who are producing research software actively: approximately 300-500 unique people. Of these folks, we received responses from 28 heliophysics researchers to date and we report those results here.

NOTE: The poll is still open and is accepting input (see QR code below).

<https://forms.gle/MqJw4f6hQ6ix8e6e6>

<https://tinyurl.com/HelioSoftware>

Figure 2 shows that we sampled across a distribution of research areas from subdomains of Heliophysics. The space weather and plasma physics communities appear to be underrepresented although the catch-all category of “Heliophysics” may contain members of these communities. 28 respondents indicated that the survey samples the broader community within an ~18% error (2-sigma confidence interval, survey sample community size assumed to be approximately 500 members). This indicates there is a significant error on the answers and is a source of concern. However, as we will show below, it is not so large a sampling error as to prevent us from making some initial conclusions about community software use.

What broad science category(ies) does the work you perform in this software environment fall into?

28 responses

Figure 2. Shows the survey had broad heliophysics researcher engagement although some sub-domains remain underrepresented, particularly aeronomy, plasma physics and space weather (which are possibly hidden within the 'heliophysics' category). We plan to continue to poll the community to help further flesh out these missing communities' software behavior.

Much of the results of the survey are user-supplied text answers and we considered how these may be grouped together to draw insights about common behavior. Along these lines, one main result we extracted was to collate the science task each respondent used in their described software environment. We used GPT4all with the Mistral OpenOrca model (Lian et al, 2023) and found that we could group the answers fairly well into four broad categories of tasks (see Figure 3).

Figure 3. Bucketting of survey responses can be grouped into four broad categories of software tasks.

Of the four software task categories, “Data processing and Analysis Tools” is the largest grouping by total number of similar responses (25). Within the sampling error, all task categories are significantly above 0 respondents and this indicates these are likely legitimate groupings of software tasks for the Heliophysics community (although additional data may rejigger components of some of these tasks into slightly different groupings). Even with the given survey error, the “Data Processing and Analysis Tools” task is significantly more popular than the other categories and we can reasonably infer that this is likely the most common task category in the broader community.

Figure 4. Histogram of top 100 occurring packages from the survey.

Figure 4 shows the top 100 packages by occurrence. Somewhat surprisingly ‘tornado’, a high-performance web framework and asynchronous networking library, occurs about as

frequently as 'astropy', an astronomical python software support package. The popularity of the Tornado package might indicate that there is a very common need for heliophysics software to interconnect with other services, clients and sites on the internet.

Discussion

The survey results point to a possible solution – to tailor a number of virtual software environments and associated images around the software task categories. This strategy would naturally break up and limit the number of included software packages and (hopefully) decrease the size and complexity of the environments. We plan to examine the survey responses to identify packages by the software task category and see if there is any significant difference between the assorted packages in each. Where we can determine that the software package collection for a task is significantly different, we'll experiment with building images both to see if we can derive smaller sizes and to test them with representatives of these communities to assess their utility for the task. Of course, more survey data would also be desirable to better define categories and software packages in use.

Each software environment we create will be made easily available (e.g. through the cloud platforms mentioned) and citable with version controlled DOIs. Doing so allows us to help overcome a critical barrier to research transparency - a pillar of open science. Making each version-controlled software environment citable will additionally increase the transparency and reproducibility of the science result that built that work.

Summary

We have conducted a survey of the heliophysics research software development community and found that we can identify four broad software tasks which the community engages in. Our survey included capturing the python software packages which the developers utilize but if we create software environments which include most of these packages we produce prohibitively large container images and create virtual software environments which have challenges for resolving the many 3rd party dependencies, making downstream use by consumers problematic. A possible resolution to these issues is to mine our survey data to map the software packages needed by software task category, and then create virtual software environments and associated container images which target each software task category.

This work has only just begun. We expect to continue our outreach efforts, work towards producing these shared software environments, and plan to report on refined results in a future paper.

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